

Separation and Identification of Tranquilizers in Biological Material by Thin Layer Chromatography

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A tlc technique has been applied for the detection and identification of eleven important 1,4-benzodiazepine derivatives. A method for their extraction from tissues has also been suggested.

THE use of 1,4-benzodiazepine derivatives has increased over other tranquilizers. The present work describes a rapid and reliable method for the qualitative and quantitative determination of 1,4-benzodiazepines by means of thin layer chromatography¹, and the application of this technique towards the study of the aforementioned substances in biological fluids and commercial drugs. It may be qualitatively identified at concentrations of 0.2 mg dm⁻³ or more.

Table 1 records the data of tlc separation of several 1,4-benzodiazepine derivatives. All derivatives are distinctly separated from each other as is evident from the R_f values. Further, these benzodiazepines were found to exhibit distinctly coloured

reagents. The drug extracted from the biological material could be successfully detected and identified from the R_f value and colour of the spot on tlc plate (Table 2).

TABLE 2— R_f VALUE AND COLOUR OF DIFFERENT EXTRACTED 1,4-BENZODIAZEPINE DERIVATIVES ON Tlc PLATE

Solvent system : ether - n-hexane (80 : 20, v/v), chamber saturation : unsaturated, solvent front = 15 cm, time of running = 2.40 h, temp = 32°, humidity = 75%

Drug	R_f × 100	Uv-light colour of spot after exposure NO ₂	Bratton - Marshall reagent	Dragendroff reagent
Chlordiazepoxide	11	Orange	Reddish	Reddish orange
Nitrazepam	20	Light purple	Light yellow	Orange
	26	Light reddish	Light yellow	Orange red
Oxazepam	28	Purple violet	Reddish	Orange
	36	Reddish	Violet	Violet red
Flurazepam	11	Greenish yellow	Yellowish orange (faint)	Yellowish orange
Diazepam	46	Yellow	Orange	Yellowish orange
	64	Yellow	Orange	Orange red
Lorazepam	33	Orange reddish	Orange	Light violet
Lormetazepam	25	Yellow	Red	Purple violet
Bromazepam	47	Yellow	Orange red	Purple orange
	37	Brown yellow	Purple violet	Orange red
Medazepam	38	Dark	Yellow	Orange
	72	Dark	Yellow	Orange
Temazepam	26	Light yellow	Orange red	Orange red
	20	Yellow	Orange red	Orange red
Prazepam	86	Yellow	Yellowish orange	Yellow orange

TABLE 1— R_f VALUE AND COLOUR OF DIFFERENT 1,4-BENZODIAZEPINE DERIVATIVES ON Tlc PLATE

Solvent system : ether - n-hexane (80 : 20, v/v), chamber saturation : unsaturated, solvent front = 15 cm, time of running = 2.40 h, temp = 32°, humidity = 75%

Drug	R_f × 100	Uv-light colour of spot after exposure NO ₂	Bratton - Marshall reagent	Dragendroff reagent
Chlordiazepoxide	10	Orange	Reddish	Reddish orange
Nitrazepam	25	Light reddish	Light yellow	Orange red
Oxazepam	36	Reddish	Violet	Violet
Flurazepam	11	Greenish yellow	Yellowish orange (faint)	Yellowish orange
Diazepam	64	Yellow	Orange (faint)	Yellowish orange
Lorazepam	33	Orange reddish	Orange (faint)	Light violet
Lormetazepam	17	Yellow	Orange red	Purple violet
Bromazepam	37	Brown yellow	Purple violet	Orange red
Medazepam	72	Dark	Yellow	Orange
Temazepam	50	Yellow	Orange red	Orange red
Prazepam	86	Yellow	Yellowish orange	Yellowish orange

spots on tlc plate when viewed under uv light (254 nm) after NO₂ exposure. All the drugs responded to both Bratton - Marshall and Dragendroff

Experimental

The procedure is based on the acid hydrolysis of 1,4-benzodiazepines to their corresponding amino-

benzophenone derivatives, and their analysis by tlc have been previously described².

Standard tlc equipment and analytical grade reagents were used. Silica gel G (0.25 mm) on glass plates (20 × 20 cm) and solvent system ether – hexane (80 : 20, v/v) were used.

Bartton–Marshall reagent³ was prepared by dissolving *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine hydrochloride (1.0 g) in ethanol (10 ml).

Dragendroff's reagent⁴ stock solution was prepared by mixing equal volumes of solution A (0.85 g basic bismuth nitrate dissolved in a mixture of 10 ml acetic acid and 60 ml of water) and solution B (8.0 g KI in 20 ml water), and the spray reagent was prepared by mixing the stock solution (1.0 ml) with acetic acid (20 ml) and water (10 ml) before use.

Extraction : A mixture of tissues or other biological samples (20 g) and (NH₄)₂SO₄ (10 g) was homogenised with ethanol (30 ml). The material was acidified with a few drops of acetic acid and refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. After cooling, the solution was filtered and concentrated to 10 ml. It was then diluted with water (30 ml) and dilute HCl (2 ml), shaken and transferred to a separatory funnel. The aqueous solution was extracted with 40 ml portions of chloroform–ether (1 : 3) by shaking for 5 min each time, twice in acidic medium, in neutral medium and lastly in alkaline medium by adding ammonia to the aqueous solution. All the extracted organic solvent fractions were combined, washed with water (20 ml), dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄) and evaporated to dryness. The residue was taken up in chloroform (10 ml) for tlc analysis.

Procedure : Glass plates (20 × 20 cm) coated with a slurry of silica gel G (0.25 mm thickness) were dried at room temperature. The plates were then activated at 110° for 30 min before use. Ethanolic solution (5 ml; 1 mg ml⁻¹) of control drugs (5 ml; 1 mg ml⁻¹), viz. chlordiazepoxide, oxazepam, nitrazepam, flurazepam, diazepam, lorazepam, lormetazepam, bromazepam, medazepam, temazepam and prazepam were applied to the plate as separate spots and developed at ambient temperature of 32° with the solvent system ether – n-hexane (8 : 2, v/v). After 15 cm run, the plate was exposed for 1 min to NO₂ vapours (prepared by the action of concentrated HNO₃ on copper turnings), and

then kept in air to remove excess of NO₂ from the tlc plate. The plate was then viewed under uv light (254 nm) and then sprayed with Bratton – Marshall and Dragendroff reagents.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 records the separation and identification of eleven 1,4-benzodiazepine derivatives with distinct coloured spots located with different R_f values. But in case of extracted drugs (Table 2), in addition to the identical spots due to the original drugs, some other coloured spots with different R_f values are also observed. This indicates that some metabolites formation has taken place in these cases. However, the tlc technique is quite reliable for the separation and identification of 1,4-benzodiazepine derivatives.

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